

A Standardized Framework for Spatiotemporal Documentation of Cultural Heritage Objects

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Abstract: To identify and track the provenance of cultural objects, experts need to follow certain rules and guidelines that help them to organize and share information. This leads to the adoption of standardized frameworks for providing a consistent way of documenting cultural objects and ensuring the interoperability, semantic enrichment and long-term preservation of information. The EU-funded ENIGMA project focuses on endorsing the safeguarding, protection, and provenance management of cultural objects. In this context, involved parties such as Legal Enforcement Agencies officers and archaeologists need to study and document the objects to identify their provenance in both space and time. This paper explores the integration of Europeana, the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM), Getty Vocabularies, and Dublin Core metadata standards within a Geographic Information System (GIS) environment to develop a structured, interoperable, and semantically rich model for managing the spatiotemporal dimensions of cultural heritage data and therefore a standardized framework to support the monitoring of the provenance of potential looted cultural objects.

CIDOC CRM provides an ontological framework for modeling cultural heritage entities and their complex relationships over time, facilitating the identification of the provenance of cultural objects and the associations between them. The controlled vocabularies at The Getty (the Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN), and Union List of Artist Names (ULAN)) are used to standardize the terminology of the descriptive attribute features. The Dublin Core and the Europeana Data Model (EDM) are used to standardise metadata and make digital resources interoperable to larger cultural property networks.

In parallel, the integration of a GIS infrastructure enhances the ability to represent, analyse and visualise the spatial and temporal routes of cultural objects, allowing researchers to reconstruct historical routes, map the presence of objects and study their patterns' appearance over different periods.

A key challenge in the use of Information Technologies in cultural heritage management is the integration of heterogeneous data sources [1], documenting the movement, ownership and natural or contextual changes of cultural heritage objects. This paper presents a methodological approach to encoding and visualizing these dynamics in a GIS-based environment, incorporating temporal ontologies and spatial analysis to enable detailed reconstruction of an object's historical presence and documented routes. Leveraging the principles of linked object data and semantic web technologies, the proposed model supports the creation of knowledge graphs that link objects, locations and historical events, enabling advanced spatiotemporal analysis of cultural heritage data.

1. Introduction

The provenance, origin, ownership history and documented routes through space and time of cultural heritage (CH) objects are of profound interest to the disciplines of archaeology and museology but are also fundamental in the battle against illicit trafficking [2]. Provenance does not just provide historical and cultural context, it also plays a role in verifying the authenticity and legal ownership of an artifact. The growing and varying number of threats against cultural heritage has sparked a renewed interest in documenting the origin of CH objects. Indeed, the illegal excavations for movable cultural objects have increased globally and so has the illicit transport of such objects across borders through trafficking. This phenomenon demonstrates how vulnerable tangible cultural heritage, particularly of smaller sizes, has become and proves the significant gaps and pitfalls in the current documentation and tracking systems. Under this spectrum, cultural heritage professionals need efficient and systematic instruments to monitor an object's history and to identify potential discrepancies. These threats also highlight the need for robust, interoperable and semantically consistent documentation frameworks, which can guarantee not only the maintenance of cultural data but also the preservation of their contextual information through time and across institutions.

Numerous agents—archaeologists, curators, cultural ministries, law enforcement agencies—participate in the process of analyzing and managing provenance data. Standardized documentation is essential for such multidisciplinary collaboration. Standards are the technical basis for sustainable and accessible data, while semantic technologies pool information through converting, combining, discovering and extracting knowledge across (previously) isolated systems by using the principles of Linked Open Data. Ontological models like the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM), and metadata schemas, like the Dublin Core and the Europeana Data Model (EDM), are instrumental in developing such a communication network. Such standards enable the modeling of complex relations between cultural objects, creators, historical events, and places over time. In addition to these models, Getty Research Institute's Controlled Vocabularies such as Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT), Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN), and Union List of Artist Names (ULAN) can increase semantic accuracy and cross-domain multilingual inter-connectability. In this context, the ENIGMA project funded by the European Union aims to develop a Common Infrastructure for the Protection, Security and Ownership Provenance Management of Cultural objects [3]. The proposed methodology can enable the documentation of provenance's spatial and temporal dimensions that have not been considered until recently as equally important to other parameters. By integrating metadata standards with geospatial analysis tools, ENIGMA is designed to leverage the hierarchical structure of the LOD of objects and conduct an analysis to uncover patterns, gaps and suspicious signs of movement.

This article introduces a spatiotemporal documentation model that provides the basis for harmonising metadata standards and ontological frameworks in a GIS context. This enables the visualization and analysis of cultural objects in space and time establishing relations between them. It can also improve the tracking of heritage provenance, reveal any unusual records in the documentation and facilitate decision-making processes for the protection of cultural heritage. The proposed model serves in the detection of potential illicit trafficking routes and the improvement of the institutional capacity in cultural heritage documentation, preservation and cross-border cooperation, providing a scalable and interoperable framework for the provenance tracing of the 21st century.

2. Documentation Standards and Semantic Integration for Heterogeneous Cultural Heritage Data

Documentation of cultural heritage is of a diverse and complex nature, ranging from textual excavation records and scholarly interpretations to museum catalogs and legal documentation, photos, and geospatial data. This variety in involved professional disciplines, file formats, and existing terminologies constitutes a major

challenge for consistency, interoperability, and long-term preservation of data between institutions and digital platforms.

The lack of common standards can lead to fragmented data integration, lower levels of data discoverability and potentially ambiguous or even contradictory information, particularly in complex processes like provenance tracking. In this context, the use of Linked Open Data (LOD) principles represents a game-changing solution for connecting cultural heritage data from different sources, formats, and themes. LOD provides structured and semantically enriched descriptions of cultural objects and events, thus facilitating the ability to discover relationships and new contexts [4].

At the core of such an approach is the existence of ontologies and metadata standards that are able to consistently encode information and represent the conceptual and informative richness of cultural heritage narratives. The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) is a fundamental ontology that formalises events, actors, places, and objects and their complex interrelations in time. CIDOC CRM allows for provenance to be described as a network of related entities and events, by recording the entire lifecycle of a cultural object from its creation and modification to its acquisition, movement and change of context. For example, the CRM class “E57-Material indicates” the dressing materials of an item, “E29-Design or Procedure” involves the technologies used, and “E52 Time-Span” frames it in time.

Supporting this ontological backbone are metadata standards such as the Europeana Data Model (EDM) and Dublin Core, which have been developed to provide loose yet expansive metadata interchange across digital heritage infrastructures. EDM is built upon the Dublin Core vocabulary while extending it to include a description of the relationship between metadata records, aggregations, and their multiple representations (particularly important for aggregating diverse datasets).

These models are prevalent in pan-European frameworks and are operated to ensure that digital content can be exchanged and linked in a meaningful way between repositories and countries. Simultaneously, the adoption of controlled vocabularies becomes more important to semantic harmonization. Integrating Getty Vocabularies in documentation workflows results in consistent communication language that is essential for ensuring data quality, multilingual representation, and interoperability[5].

The following three important Getty tools [5] were used in this research:

1. Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) which provides a structured vocabulary for material, style, technique, object, and related concepts.
2. The Union List of Artist Names (ULAN) includes biographical information, variant names, and relational context for both individuals and corporate bodies involved in cultural production.
3. Thesaurus of Geographic Names (TGN) provides a hierarchical system of place names that are employed by categories to associate objects to their geographical context through a corresponding geographical reference.

The use of these standards in the ENIGMA project demonstrates a semantic basis for the documentation, analysis, and visualization of spatiotemporal object routes. Controlled vocabularies not only enable the integrity and accuracy of data in its initial documentation (e.g., by archaeologists and law enforcement officers) but also support downstream activities (such as provenance tracing, cultural heritage research, and data exchange among institutions). The combination set up through CIDOC CRM (ontological expressive power), EDM/Dublin Core (metadata interoperability) and Getty Vocabularies (terminological rigour) can ensure the semantic consistency, enrichment and long-term durability of an integrated cultural heritage information system and will be addressed through this proposed methodology.

3. A Spatiotemporal Approach to Cultural Object Documentation

The present research focuses on the existing standards and their integration in a common platform to overcome semantic heterogeneity and varying documentation standardization. The need to discover accurately an object's provenance is not completely addressed solely by unifying vocabularies and their respective metadata but also by focusing on documenting the cultural object's information in space and time. Provenance should not be viewed as a static characteristic, but rather as a moving chain of events in space and time, and affected by legal, historical and sociocultural changes. The CIDOC CRM acts as a strong ontological framework for modeling the lifecycle of objects but can also incorporate spatial and temporal reasoning as part of the semantic-web, complementing the GIS using relevant CRM-compatible extensions. This section outlines a methodological framework for realizing such a spatiotemporal approach, which combines event-based modeling, geographic referencing, stratigraphic logic and semantic enrichment for tracking and displaying the documented routes of cultural objects.

3.1. Combining Time and Place via Ontologies and GIS

Records of cultural object descriptors need to capture not simply “what is”, but also “what, when and where an action has taken place (made, transferred, stored, etc.)”. An effective way to achieve this goal is to combine temporal and spatial semantics in a documentation strategy. This starts with an ontological basis built on the CIDOC-CRM which, similarly to other information networks, models cultural knowledge and literacy as a network of events (E5 Event) in which people, objects, places and time stamps are identified as of equal importance.

Any cultural object (“E22-Man - Made Object”) is related to a process – for example, creation (“E12-Production”), discovery (“E63-Beginning of Existence”), acquisition (“E8-Acquisition”), or transfer (“E10-Transfer of Custody”) – that is temporarily and spatially specified through the CIDOC classes “E52 Time – Span” and “E53-Place”. These classes become nodes for adding geographical coordinates and time intervals to events recorded in an object's history.

To allow for geospatial visualization and querying, spatial entities are encoded using GeoSPARQL properties, with geometries formatted in WKT (Well-Known Text).[6] WKT format is a well-established format supported by all known commercial and open-source GIS database management systems. In the case of the present research, the implementation of the geographic management infrastructure is implemented through the PostgreSQL database enabled with Post GIS capabilities, which allows for spatial indexing, spatial joins, proximity search and other geospatial analysis operators [4].

3.2. Representing the Lifecycle of Cultural Objects using CIDOC CRM

The event-driven approach of the CIDOC CRM is particularly useful for capturing the provenance and routes of the cultural objects in time. Instead of directly assigning objects with properties, it describes what the objects have done. For instance, an event of illegal excavation can be described as an “E7-Activity” that occurred at a particular “E53-Place” and was carried out by one or more “E39-Actors” (i.e. looters, traffickers, LEAs, archeologists) [7].

Each event should be linked to specific classes and properties. The present approach focuses on:

- Time span (P4 has time-span -> ”E52-Time-Span”),
- Took place at (P7 was performed at → “E53-Place”),

- Participants (P14 performed by → “E39-Actor”),
- Object (P12 occurred with → “E22-Man-Made Object”).

This pathway facilitates an efficient event-based modeling structure of evolving, time-sensitive object history. As reported by Pasin & Motta [8], event-centric models support the tracking of knowledge evolution. The application of this approach in the cultural heritage domain allows deeper exploration and reuse of cultural object documentation information.

Using CIDOC CRM’s “E53-Place” by incorporating the WKT format provides the ability to monitor routes of cultural objects - from excavation sites to collectors, museums, illegal distribution sites etc. These spatial components are indexed and searched with GIS technology which allows:

- Discovery of provenance patterns across administrative borders, conflict areas, heritage sites, etc.
- Creation of spatial timelines and animated views depicting the progression and geographical paths of objects.

For instance, a cultural object may be documented by its excavation coordinates (“P7-took place at”), transit route (“E9-Move”), and exhibition location (“P55-has current location”). This spatial data can be visualized using a GIS and further analyse correlation with other objects, taking into account spatiotemporal relationships through more analytical algorithms. The scope of this approach is to manage to query the implemented model to define the temporal relationships between two or more objects having recorded events/presence in the location. (Figure 1).

Temporal Relation	Definition
A before B	
A is equal to B	
A meets B	

Figure 1: Topological relationships between two-time signals of intervals A and B [9]

3.3. Enriching Semantics in Temporal Scene Completion

As already stated, the heterogeneity of the data is managed using controlled vocabularies (with an emphasis on those from the Getty Research Institute – AAT, ULAN, TGN) and further used to contribute to the semantic coherence and interoperability. Each vocabulary covers different aspects:

- AAT specifications (Materials E57, Design or Procedure E29 etc.).
- TGN is made up of historical and current geographical names associated with “E53-Place”,
- ULAN enables identity resolution for creators, collectors, or actors by adding “E39-Actor”.

These vocabularies have been integrated into operational applications where LEA officers or archaeologists adopt rapid-entry documentation systems to ensure term consistency while in the field or during initial object analysis.

Incorporating the semantic enrichment on both time and place information enhances the spatiotemporal analysis providing the following advantages:

- Automatic inference of missing steps in an object's path (e.g., corresponding gaps between recorded events).
- Cross-institutional and international cross-references,
- Object movement linked to history (such as wars or looting areas etc.).

4. Modeling Cultural Object Presence and Path Construction

The life of a cultural object should not be conceived as static information, but a record of past presences – that is, points in time and space at which an object was materially or symbolically located, by way of moments such as; production, recovery, acquirement, documentation, or illegal trafficking. Every “presence,” therefore, is not only a trace but also a geospatial-temporal node within the evolving object’s routes. By modeling this presence and paths, its appearance is not only available for ‘reconstruction’ but can also be actively searched for.

4.1. Defining Presence in the Context of Cultural Heritage (Events, Locations and Dates)

According to the CIDOC CRM, the presence of an object is represented by the events that the object participates in (“E5-Event” and its subclasses), and that information is added to its context by providing a place and date of existence. Presence can refer to:

- Fieldwork, based on physical excavation at an archaeological site (“E7-Activity”, Excavation Process Unit),
- Acquisition as part of a collection (“E8-Acquisition” or “E10-Transfer of Custody”) of the material,
- Public exhibition (“E7-Activity” or custom subclasses),
- Transportation or relocation (“E9-Move”).

Each of these cases is temporally bounded (“E52-Time-Span”), and spatially specific (“E53-Place”) thus creating a spatiotemporal trace of the object's path. Each event needs to be assigned the following additional information:

- A start and end date for the Event (P4 has time-span → “E52-Time-Span”),
- A geographic location (P7 took place at → “E53-Place”),
- The cultural object(s) that were present (P12 occurred in the presence of (was present at)→ “E22 Human-Made Object”),
- The actor(s) involved (P14 carried out by (performed) → “E39-Actor”).

When written in RDF, these relations enable the formation of structured provenance chains. Each event instance becomes a node linking entities, agents, time and location, serving as the backbone for a spatiotemporal knowledge graph.

4.2. Visualizing Cultural Objects “routes” with GIS

GIS provides a platform for plotting these object’s locations over time and space. Each “E53-Place” is encoded by geographic coordinates via spatial data formats like WKT or GeoJSON and imported to a GIS backend provider (e.g. PostGIS.). Visualization of Time Series Data is possible using event interval-centric timelines, simple animation of years or space using one of the various tools for web GIS implementation, composite mapping excavation layers, ownership history, and transportation paths.

GIS tools allow users to:

- follow the physical curation of an item (e.g. from an excavation site to a museum),
- detect discrepancies including ownership transfer leaps and undocumented location gaps, and,
- compare multiple objects’ “routes” to discover patterns of trade, looting, or collecting.

5. Implementation within the ENIGMA Project

The ENIGMA project is setting the described spatiotemporal approach into practice through a functional, role-based platform with the simple goal of helping with the provenance identification, and monitoring of cultural goods (CGs) that are under potential looting, or illicit trafficking threat. It connects semantic modeling on CIDOC CRM with modular integration of GIS, remote sensing, and AI-based similarity analysis, providing a new type of heritage intelligence infrastructure. In this section, the application of this framework and the tools that realize the spatiotemporal heritage research in real world context are explored.

5.1. Unified Platform Access and Navigation

Upon authentication, LEA officers and experts (e.g., archaeologists or curators) access the ENIGMA platform through a role-based interface. As shown in Figure 2, users are presented with a navigation panel tailored to their roles, giving them access to:

- the Provenance Research Tool, (**Figure 2**)
- the Remote Sensing Alerts Toolkit, and,
- the Crowdsourcing Hotspot Analysis Module.

Figure 2: Navigation panel for expert access to provenance analysis, remote sensing results, and crowdsourcing heatmap tools.

This integrated workspace enables professionals to work with semantically structured cultural object data, link object moments in time and places, and, more importantly, project provenance knowledge outward into the spatial domain for monitoring and risk detection.

5.2. Stepwise Workflow: From LEA Screening to Expert Review

The process initiates with the LEA officer’s initial screening, involving the submission of the cultural object’s descriptive data and photographic documentation. The User Interface’s (UI) Supporting tools propose a standard term from Getty and other vocabularies. After selection, hierarchical links pointing to the Linked Open Data can be added to improve the level of data structuring (**Figure 3**).

Figure 3: Documentation interface for LEA officers. Getty vocabularies support LOD-enhanced terminology suggestion and semantic structuring.

The expert’s review follows, enriching the record with historical, stylistic, and geospatial context. As shown in **Figure 4**, archaeologists can specify origin hypotheses, excavation dates, cultural periods, and movement patterns—all aligned to CIDOC CRM and its extensions.

Figure 4: Documentation interface for archaeologists. Experts enrich the record using standardized fields and Getty LOD-enhanced values.

All recorded data is mapped to CIDOC CRM classes. Object presences are linked to:

- “E5-Event” (e.g. excavation, transfer, exhibition),
- “E52-Time-Span” (for temporal bounding),
- “E53-Place” (for geospatial anchoring using WKT or coordinate pairs),
- “E39-Actor” (for participants or institutions).

Currently, the spatiotemporal search is mostly being used to discover and propose areas of interest for lower-level tools such as the Remote Sensing Toolkit and the Public Participation Module. By examining the database of object presence events (i.e. origins, discovery, transportation, etc.) and the temporal clustering of documented cultural movements, the system identifies regions that are likely to be relevant in the provenance gaps/looting activity. (Figure 5) While these zones are not at present employed for dynamic “routes” modeling, they guide experts to areas that deserve further investigation through the remote sensing tools and hotspot analysis from the public participation module. This selective application of spatiotemporal reasoning to the results contributes to the efficiency and ease in the development of precise expert-driven as well as collaborative heritage monitoring.

Figure 5: Remote Sending toolkit providing areas related to the objects’ “presence”

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This article proposed a spatiotemporal model for cultural object documentation by incorporating existing ontologies, metadata standards, and geospatial analysis tools. By using EDM with the CIDOC CRM, CRMarchaeo [10] and Getty-controlled vocabularies, ENIGMA allows for the structured recording, enrichment and interpretation of cultural object documentation in the dimensions of time and space. The model provides a means to connect cultural heritage objects with a specific time and place, allowing experts and law enforcement agents to investigate cultural objects’ provenance, and detect potential illicit trafficking.

Taking a semantically rich and standardized approach, ENIGMA fills a long-standing gap in cultural heritage documentation: namely to describe objects not just as artifacts, but as located entities in the spatiotemporal space. This can facilitate the verification of provenance, promote interoperability with other institutions and reinforce collaboration on the cross-border fight against illicit trafficking in the cultural property domain and of course allow its repatriation. This is achieved by incorporating the standardized approach focusing on Linked Open Data for durable and discoverable object records, and ontologies to map complex relationships, such as transfers, excavations and exhibitions, to semantic connections.

Future developments should preferably focus on the following proposed enhancements to make the system smarter and more adaptive:

- Integration with broader international data sets will be extended through federated SPARQL queries and linkage with international heritage registries and linked open data stores. This will give rise to cross-institutional provenance graphs and facilitate better object matching between countries.

- Improved Visualization and User Interface Tools - Dynamic “routes” maps, timeline-based visual navigation, and modular interfaces for various user groups (archaeologists, law enforcement, curators) are contemplated. Automated reasoning and AI-enhanced inference will aid in discovering undocumented gaps in provenance, pattern recognition of the route of looted objects, and predictive modeling of suspicious objects. The integration of CRMarchaeo [10] into ENIGMA’s modeling framework provides possibilities for more in-depth temporal reasoning. These stratigraphic entities, such as “Excavation Process Unit”, “Stratigraphic Unit” and others, will provide the basis for representing relative timelines in cases where absolute date information is absent. These properties facilitate archaeological reasoning about temporal sequencing, even in dataset-poverty situations, and supply the semantic infrastructure to generate inferred occupation phases from excavation data. Together with the availability of spatial data access services and tools like Geotriples or federated RDF stores, will provide the ability to support advanced queries on both semantic and geospatial aspects.

In summary, the ENIGMA architecture provides a solid, flexible, and interoperable platform for current and future research into cultural heritage provenance in the digital era. It aligns the semantic web principles with the requirements of on-the-ground object tracking and provenance research to support the fight against illicit trafficking.

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